

Thermal performance analysis of thermal energy storage tank using solid rocks with HITEC salt

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Abstract: A thermocline thermal energy storage (TES) tank is the key element in storing thermal energy for concentrated solar power (CSP) plants. This paper focuses on the thermal analysis of the single-stage thermal energy storage (TES) tank by using molten Hitec salt, which is a eutectic mixture of 7 wt% NaNO₃, 40 wt% NaNO₂ and 53 wt% KNO₃. This molten salt is used as heat transfer media and solid quartzite rock is used as filler materials. The Dispersion-Concentric model, based on energy equations and solved by the finite element method, is used to study the heat transfer module for the computational domain. The research presents the 3D temperature domain for heat transfer fluid (HTF) and filler materials inside the TES tank. The temperature profile of HTF and solid materials are also plotted as a tank height and time function. As the value of thermal conductivity and specific heat capacity of HTF is higher than that of the solid filler materials, we found that the temperature of HTF is greater than that of the solid rock at the same time at a specific tank height.

Keywords: Thermocline, Solar, Renewable Energy, Molten Salt, Computational, Dispersion-Concentric, Hitec salt

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Introduction

In renewable energy sectors, solar power becomes an attractive form of renewable energy for its abundance in nature. Solar energy is the radiant light and heat that the sun emits, and it is captured through a variety of ever-evolving technologies including photovoltaics, solar thermal energy, solar architecture, molten salt power plants, and artificial photosynthesis. It is a crucial source of renewable energy and depending on how solar energy is captured, distributed, or transformed into solar power, its technologies are broadly characterized as passive solar or active solar. A thermocline, also known as the thermal layer, is a thin but distinct layer within a massive body of fluid (such as water in an ocean or lake, or air in the atmosphere), where the temperature fluctuates more drastically with depth than it does within the layers above or below. The thermocline in the ocean separates the turbulent upper mixed layer from the tranquil deep

water below. In the tank where molten salt is kept as a source of thermal energy in the CSP plant, the thermocline is frequently visible. A thermocline thermal energy storage system is the key element of the CSP plant which is used to store hot molten salts that have been melted by the concentrated heat of the sun. The tank is filled with solid rocks which are used as filler materials and molten salts as heat transfer media. Hot and cold fluids are stored in the same tank, and they are separated for their thermal stratification [1].

Traditional thermocline tanks have two tanks where hot and cold fluids are kept separate, whereas thermocline TES tanks save money by employing just one tank to serve both purposes. During the charging cycle, hot fluid is pushed from the top of the tank, and during the discharging cycle, cold fluid is pumped from the bottom. The fluid in the tank moves slowly, and filler materials are used to keep the thermocline in place. Due to its simpler heat transfer design and advanced technology, the sensible heat storage tank has grown in popularity [2].

There are numerous ways to store solar energy. Thermal energy storage, electrical energy storage, chemical energy storage, mechanical energy storage, and electromagnetic energy storage comprise the primary storage system. Sensible heat storage and latent heat storage are further categories for thermal energy storage systems. According to the concept of sensible heat storage, substances that change internal energy can vary in temperature and store thermal energy. When the material releases or absorbs energy as the temperature changes, sensible heat is produced [3]. The characteristics of heat storage are storage medium has high specific heat capacity, long-term stability under thermal cycling, and low thermal conductivity. The storage medium is the most important component of energy storage. The sensible heat storage system uses the rock, water, concrete, brick, engine oil, and ethanol as its storage medium [3-6].

Utilizing mirror and lens technologies, the high light intensity will be concentrated in a compact region. This concentration causes the receiver to take up energy from the concentrator and transfer it to the process being driven (engine, chemical reactor, etc.). When concentrated light is converted to heat and used to power a turbine or engine, electrical power is created. Trough, tower, parabolic, and Fresnel reflectors are the four main categories of thermal concentrating solar power (CSP) systems.

In order to generate electricity at night, solar thermal energy must be stored. A thermocline thermal energy storage tank stores sensible heat in a single tank. Three zones—a hot fluid zone at the top, a cold fluid zone at the bottom, and an intermediary zone—is known as the thermocline-coexist in the tank practically constantly. By adding solids to the tank, it is possible to cut costs while maintaining thermal stratification during standby times. Only the CSP tower and trough use the store. There are several ways to store energy, however, the following are the most crucial:

Two-Tank Direct System

The same fluid is used to collect heat and store it. Two separate tanks are used to store the fluid: one for high temperatures and the other for low temperatures. When fluid from the second tank is launched to the receiver, it heats up to an extremely high temperature, which is then kept in the high-temperature tank before being flown to the heat exchanger to create steam, which will then be used to generate power when needed [7].

Two-Tank Indirect System

Two-tank indirect systems work in the same way as two-tank direct systems, but there are two different fluids, one for heat transfer and another for storage [8]. Direct systems require less piping and ancillary equipment to be added to the plant, making them easier to integrate. Indirect systems, however, require an extra line and heat exchanger. Beyond this though, the same modeling approach can be applied to both systems by merely substituting the properties of the working fluid (s).

Single Tank Mixed-Media Thermocline System

Once the tank volume has been reduced to a minimum using a single tank thermocline system, the next step in reducing the capital cost of the storage system is to reduce the cost of the storage fluid. In order to save money on high-pressure plumbing systems, organic heat transfer oils are commonly employed in high-temperature solar energy systems. Unfortunately, most organic heat-transfer oils are expensive. Mixed-media thermocline storage, also known as packed bed storage systems, seeks to displace expensive heat-transfer oil inventory in storage with less expensive materials such as rock and sand [9].

Different numerical methods describing the performance of latent packed bed TES systems are available in the literature [10,11]. Schumann’s model is applied by researchers [12-14] in which the tank is filled with distinct solid spheres, forming a continuous porous structure, which is heated or cooled by moving fluid. The Dispersion-Concentric model is used where thermal gradient inside the solid particles is considered. Ismail and Henriquez [15] investigated experimental and numerical studies based on the dispersion-concentric (D-C) model for phase change materials. Lui et al. [16] analyzed transient characteristics of the molten salt FLiNaK (46.5%LiF-11.5%NaF-42%KF) for the TES tank compared the results with HITEC (7%NaNO₃-49%NaNO₂-44%KNO₃) salt. Azam and Mamun [17] also analyzed the thermal performance of multi-layered thermal energy storage tanks using different phase change materials.

Geometry

A thermocline thermal energy storage tank is an inherent part of the CSP power plant. Figure 1 and Figure 2 are the detailed representation of the CSP plant loop and TES tank respectively. The fluid used in the main loop in a CSP plant is molten salt, which is melted using concentrated solar power to reach the required high temperature. During daytime molten salt directly goes to the heat exchanger where steam is produced as well as fills the energy storage tank. The action is referred to as the charging process.

Fig. 1: Schematic Layout of CSP power plant [18]

However, when sunlight is not available at night, the stored molten salt in the storage tank is used to create steam, which is then used to generate electricity. This is known as discharging process. Another cycle in the secondary loop is also active simultaneously where steam is the working fluid. Steam produced in the steam generator is superheated in the steam superheater section and expands in the turbine. Then the steam is condensed in the condenser where a feed pump pumps the condensate to the steam generator.

Fig. 2: Schematic diagram of three-layer storage tank

In the thermocline storage tank, heat transfer fluid enters through the inlet section and exits through the outlet section. In the distributor region, molten salt is distributed to make the flow uniform. The velocity of the molten salt is too low to maintain the thermocline in the TES tank. In this study multi-layered TES tank of different phase change materials is used. We analyzed thermal performance using solid materials by filling the whole tank and showed how the temperature changed along with the bed height. In this study, the tank wall is considered fully insulated i.e., no heat can pass through the tank wall. The main characteristics of the physical model are demonstrated in table 1.

Table 1. Main characteristics of the thermocline tank.

Parameters	Values
Height of tank (H)	0.5 m
Diameter of tank (D_{bed})	0.5 m
Diameter of PCM capsule (d_p)	0.01 m
Mass flow rate (\dot{m})	0.1 kg/s
Hot fluid temperature (T_h)	450 °C
Cold fluid temperature (T_c)	250 °C
Porosity (ϵ)	0.28

Heat Transfer Fluids and Phase Change Materials

Sodium nitrate-sodium nitrite-potassium nitrate ($\text{NaNO}_3\text{-NaNO}_2\text{-KNO}_3$) mixture may have composition in the range of (7-49-44 mol%, 7-40-53 wt.%) [19]. The melting point of commercial Hitec salt is 142 °C [20, 21] and its thermal stability is 530 °C under an inert gas atmosphere [22]. In our research work, we used the following correlation for the thermo-physical properties [23] of Hitec salt.

Density,

$$\rho \text{ (kg/m}^3\text{)} = 2279.799 - 0.7324 T \text{ (K)} \tag{1}$$

Viscosity,

$$\mu \text{ (Pa.s)} = \exp(-4.343 - 2.0143 ((\ln(T(K) - 273) - 5.0011))) \tag{2}$$

Specific heat capacity,

$$C_p \left(\frac{J}{kg.K} \right) = 1560 \tag{3}$$

Thermal conductivity,

$$k \left(\frac{W}{m.K} \right) = 0.48 \tag{5}$$

The solid medium chosen for this research work is quartzite rocks and sand. Two sizes are used in the storage tank to obtain the void fraction of about 0.25-0.30. Thus, this concept reduces the quantity of HTF used in conventional thermocline storage by about 75% [24] Top and bottom manifolds are employed to distribute the heat transfer fluid across the cross-section of the tank. The properties of HTF are functions of temperature while the solid particles have constant properties. The main characteristics of the quartzite rock and silica sand are demonstrated in table 2.

Table 2. Main characteristics of the quartzite rocks and sand [24, 25]

Parameters	Values
Density of solid particles	2245 kg/m ³
Thermal Conductivity	0.13 W/ (m. K)
Specific heat capacity	800 J/ (kg. K)

Governing Equations

The dispersion-concentric model, based on a special version of the energy equation, is used to construct the computational scheme for this analysis. This is a two-phase model based on the energy equation where the tank is considered as an isotropic porous medium filled with small spherical fragments. Temperature distribution inside spherical particles and axial heat conduction of fluid are taken into consideration in this model.

Continuity Equation:

$$\frac{\partial \rho_f}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \rho_f u_f}{\partial x} \tag{5}$$

Equation for fluid phase:

$$\epsilon \left(\rho_f C_{p_f} \right) \left(\frac{\partial T_f}{\partial t} + u_f \frac{\partial T_f}{\partial x} \right) = \epsilon k_{f_{eff}} \frac{\partial^2 T_f}{\partial x^2} + h_f (T_s - T_f) + h_w (T_w - T_f) \tag{6}$$

The equation for the solid phase:

$$(1 - \epsilon) \rho_s C_{p_s} \frac{\partial T_s}{\partial t} = (1 - \epsilon) k_s \frac{\partial^2 T_s}{\partial x^2} + h_f (T_f - T_s) \tag{7}$$

Thermal distribution inside solid particles can be determined from the following equation:

$$\rho_s C_{p_s} \frac{\partial T_s}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(k_s r^2 \frac{\partial T_s}{\partial r} \right) \tag{8}$$

The h_f is linked to the convective heat transfer coefficient h [26]

$$h_f = \frac{6(1-\epsilon)}{d_p} h \tag{9}$$

where d_p denotes the diameter of solid spheres. The heat transfer coefficient h can be calculated from

$$h_s = \frac{Nu k}{d_p} \tag{10}$$

Nusselt number Nu is a function of Reynolds number and Prandtl number based on particle diameter [27]:

$$Nu = 2 + 1.1 (Re^{0.6} Pr^{0.33}) \tag{11}$$

Here,

$$Re_p = \frac{\rho d_p u_f}{\epsilon \mu} \tag{12}$$

Where u_f denotes fluid velocity and

$$Pr = \frac{c_p \mu_f}{k} \tag{13}$$

Result and Discussion

The results were obtained by solving the above differential equations numerically. The heat transfer module of this numerical model was developed by a special form of energy equation called the Dispersion-Concentric (D-C) equation. As the tank is cylindrical and symmetric about its axis so the equations were solved for only the half portion of the tank. To solve the problem, our given system was subdivided into smaller, simpler parts. This was accomplished by creating a mesh of the item and applying a specific space discretization in the space dimensions. These equations were resolved using the boundary value problem formulation of the Finite Element Method (FEM). For time-dependent equations, an implicit method, the backward differentiation formula (BDF) was used. To simplify the analysis, the model is considered to be a homogeneous porous medium filled with continuous, isotropic solid particles and the flow of heat transfer fluid inside the TES tank is laminar and incompressible.

Fig. 3: 3D representation of fluid temperature inside TES tank

Figure 3 represents the three-dimensional temperature profile of fluid inside the thermal energy storage tank at 12 minutes. White color refers to the hot fluid temperature and dark red color refers to the cold fluid temperature. In this literature, cold fluid means the fluid or molten salt inside the tank which has a relatively low temperature than that of the hot molten salt. Initially, the whole tank is filled with low-temperature molten salt. As time passes hot molten salt replaces the space of low temperature fluid and after a certain period, the whole tank is filled with the hot fluid. The temperature gradient which is seen inside the TES tank is called the thermocline. The heat transfer inside the TES tank depends on the thickness of the thermocline. If the thermocline layer is thick, heat can be easily transferred from hot

fluid to the cold fluid which results in a heat loss of the hot molten inside the tank. A thin thermocline layer is preferable as heat is obstructed to flow from hot fluid to colder one.

Fig. 4: 3D representation of solid temperature inside TES tank

Figure 4 represents the three-dimensional temperature profile of solid filler materials inside the thermal energy storage tank at 12 minutes. The color representation is similar as stated before. A thermal gradient is also seen inside the TES tank. Firstly, the temperature of solid particles is the same as the molten salt’s temperature. When hot molten salt enters the tank, it replaces cold molten salt as well as starts to transfer heat to cold molten salt and solid particles. However, the thermal conductivity of heat transfer fluid (HTF) is higher than that of solid rocks, so the rate of heat transfer is more in HTF than that in solid particles. Hence, the 3D temperature profile of HTF inside the TES tank travels a longer bit depth than that of the solid particles.

Fig. 5: Temperature distributions on the storage in different times

Figure 5 shows the effect of temperature along tank axial distance at 8 minutes and 12 minutes for both heat transfer fluid (HTF) and solid filler materials. Solid lines represent the temperature of HTF, and dot-dashed lines represent the temperature of solid quartzite rocks. At 8 minutes, the temperature of the top of the tank is 450 °C for both HTF and

solid particles. However, temperature decreases gradually with the decrease of tank height and at 0.1 m of tank height, the temperature becomes almost 250 °C. If we have a close look, we observe that the curves at 8 minutes are steeper than the curves at 16 minutes. The steeper curve is the sign of the thinner thermocline layer. Here, the temperature of both HTF and quartzite rocks is displayed in the same graph for better understanding. The HTF's temperature is a little higher than that of the solid rocks which has been described clearly in the next part.

Fig. 6: Domain temperature of HTF and solid rocks

Figure 6 represents the domain temperature inside the TES tank for heat transfer fluid (HTF) and solid filler materials. Domain temperature is the average temperature of the whole tank at a certain time. At the starting point, the domain temperature of both HTF and filler materials is equal to 250 °C as the whole tank was at this temperature then. As time passes the domain temperature increases with time and reaches 450 °C. 30 minutes later of starting the charging cycle, the temperature remains constant as there is no cold fluid inside the tank and hot fluid fills the entire tank. In this figure, the solid line demonstrates the fluid temperature, and the dashed line indicates the solid particle temperature. We observe a little difference between the fluid temperature and solid filler particle temperature.

Fig. 7: Temperature distributions on the storage in different times

Figure 7 represents the temperature distribution at different times for different tank heights. Three tank heights are selected to measure the temperature of HTF and solid rocks: the bottom of the tank, middle of the tank and top of the tank. T indicates HTF temperature and T_2 indicates cold fluid temperature. This figure shows how temperature is changed at different positions of tank height. At the bottom of the tank, the temperature was 250 °C and after 10 minutes the effect of the temperature of hot fluid began to fall here. So, the temperature increased gradually and within 40 minutes the temperature at this position became 450°C which remains constant over time.

Fig. 8: Schematic diagram of three-layer storage tank

Figure 8 shows a zoomed temperature profile of heat transfer fluid and solid materials at 12 minutes. The solid blue line represents the fluid temperature, and the green dashed line represents the solid particle's temperature. From the figure, it is clear that for a particular height of the TES tank HTF's temperature is higher than that of the solid particle's temperature. At 0.22 m height of the tank, the Temperature of HTF is nearly 335.5 °C and the temperature of solid particles is 345.5 °C. Anyhow, if we draw a line parallel to the x-axis it will intersect the blue solid line first and then the green dot-dashed line which means that the isothermal contour of HTF is located below that of solid quartzite rocks. In a different way, it can be said that the temperature profile of fluid travels a bit longer distance than that of the solid materials at the same time.

Fig. 9: Temperature differences between HTF and porous medium along the axial distance

Figure 9 shows the temperature differences between HTF and porous medium along the tank axial distance at 12 minutes. The temperature difference between HTF and porous medium increases with tank height and then decreases. When hot molten salt enters the tank the temperature of cold HTF inside the tank increases more quickly than that of the solid spheres. It happens because the thermal conductivity and specific heat capacity of molten salt are larger than that of solid filler materials. Temperature spreads more quickly inside HTF than solid filler particles. So, a temperature difference is found between HTF and filler materials.

Conclusion

The current work presents a two-dimensional, transient model of a thermocline thermal energy storage tank and analyzes its thermal performance. Molten Hitec salt is used as heat transfer fluid and solid quartzite rock is used as filler material for the tank in order to reduce the cost of the overall cost. The thermophysical properties of molten salt are a function of temperature and solid rocks have constant properties. 3D representation of temperature along tank axial distance for heat transfer fluid (HTF) and solid quartzite is presented. Variations of temperatures with tank axial distance for different times are illustrated here from where the pattern of temperature distributions inside the tank can be understood easily. Domain temperature, as well as the temperature at different positions of the tank, is also presented against time for both HTF and solid rocks. For clear conception, a close picture of solid and fluid temperature differences is shown along tank height. From the thermal analysis, it can be realized that the temperature of the heat transfer fluid is slightly higher than that of the solid filler materials. The thermal conductivity and specific heat capacity of HTF are higher than that of the solid rocks, so, the heat spreads more inside the HTF. From this viewpoint, the manuscript may be considered inimitable and different from other research works. By improving thermal properties like specific heat capacity and the thermal conductivity of filler materials this investigation will open the door to new research in this field. However, this work helps us to uncover a new horizon for storing thermal energy which governs us to harness more energy from sunlight by using a concentrated solar collector.

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